

Exploring Alternative Livelihoods: Pathways to Sustainable Development for the Relocated Mining Communities of MABBEN.

Robert Salia Kamara

Gradxs Researcher for PhD in Organizational Management, IIC University of Technology, Cambodia (Enrolment No. FNR 240101), Paper Code: rskoolmoodee@gmail.com

Received: Sep 27, 2025

Accepted: Oct 27, 2025

Published: Nov 13, 2025

Abstract

The pursuit of sustainable development in the face of environmental degradation, economic uncertainty and social inequality necessitates the exploration of alternative livelihoods. Alternative livelihood programmes have been adopted as a different form of creating a means of support for people who have been deprived of their original means of livelihood as a result of an economic, social and environmental activities by either a corporate entity or government corporations or government regulations/laws. Some of these activities like in the case of the iron-ore rich MABBEN communities in the northern province of Sierra Leone, communities were relocated from their original ancestral settlements by a largescale mining company for economic or corporate reasons to the company. Alternative livelihood programmes have been seen as a viable option for underprivilege people, however, despite the enormous and increasing importance of alternative livelihood programmes in the mining industry in Sierra Leone especially in the Iron-ore rich MABBEN communities, little studies have been conducted to assess the real impacts on the inhabitants of the relocated communities of MABBEN.

This paper explores the impacts of alternative livelihood programmes and its sustainability on the relocated communities. It also examines the potential of alternative livelihoods to promote economic diversification, reduce vulnerability, and enhance well-being. Various literatures were reviewed based on the objective of the study. The method employed in this study is mixed method in which primary and secondary data were collected, interviews and focused group discussions were scheduled to collect data from inhabitants of the relocated communities as well as other key stakeholders out of the communities.

The findings suggest that alternative livelihood programmes were done for the relocated communities but they were not sustainable and could not foster economic resilience. Other findings revealed that the alternative livelihood programmes in the area of Agriculture, water and sanitation are inadequate and beneficiaries are generally not satisfied. Also, the beneficiaries indicated that adequate jobs as a form of alternative livelihood programmes as well as entrepreneurship is highly preferable. Beneficiaries also recounted the opportunities that the CDAP (Community development action plan) programme comes with if it is redesigned to enhance sustainability.

The major challenge encountered by development partners and companies in implementing alternative livelihood programmes was minimal cooperation from stakeholders. Based on the findings, it was recommended that the indigenous livelihood strategies be built on to enhance cultural sustainability. The paper also provides insights on the need to consolidate the current collaboration and redesign and broaden the scope of the current alternative livelihood programmes to fit the need of the communities and enhance sustainability. Despite the major challenges that the study revealed, the study recommends that continuous community engagement can minimize the implementation gaps that exists between the community and implementing partners.

Keywords: Alternative livelihood, cultural sustainability, Economic diversification, social inequality, Relocated Community.

Introduction

Sierra Leone is endowed with large mineral deposit such as Iron-ore, rutile, gold, diamond, ilmenite and bauxite, which are exploited in commercial quantities by small and large-scale companies and this sector has played crucial role in the country's economy. The proliferation of these companies in resource-rich MABBEN communities has resulted in mining-induced land change for local livelihood which has brought about numerous challenges including environmental degradation, economic uncertainty and social inequality. These challenges have significant impact on livelihood particularly for the vulnerable population in the relocated communities. The communities were displaced from their fertile land with a lot of ancestral and cultural endowment that makes them very comfortable to new settlements where they find it difficult to acclimatize and even after acclimatization, they find it difficult to recover from the shock, stress and the insatiable living conditions that comes with losing their lands, crops and cultural heritage. In the process, some of them have no option but to migrate to seek greener pasture elsewhere. The affected relocated communities are confronted with food, water security challenge as well as the loss of economic opportunities as a result of their relocation. The idea of relocating communities makes people confront heightened risk of social instability and human rights violation as a result of their unfamiliarity with their new locations (Adam, Owen & Kemp, 2015). Small/Large-scale mining sites are often located in area covered by forests and other types of natural features and these activities which in most cases are done with the use of sophisticated equipments and chemical substances resulting in modifications to the natural ecosystem with huge implications for the environment and local livelihoods especially in the MABBEN communities that are heavily reliant on land-based resources. There is a clear demonstration that mining activities have both a direct impact on the land use/land cover within the mining sites and the indirect effects on land change outside the mining areas. Undoubtedly, the industrial mining activities have definitely changed the local livelihood dynamics in the form of jobs within the mining sector and related industry, such changes can also result in additional problem to the communities because most of the jobs provided are inadequate menial jobs that does not come with the expected remunerations as the community people often lack the expertise to secure professional jobs demanded by mining companies. The number of mining firms in Sierra Leone has increased over the past decade and this has witnessed commensurate increase in the amount of research related to mining activities within the country and its associated effects on local livelihood. In 2018, there were six (6) large-scale and nine (9) small-scale mining companies in Sierra Leone but in 2021 to 2024 there are eleven (11) large-scale and Nineteen (19) small-scale mining companies operating in Sierra Leone (National Minerals Agency report, March 2024). Differences in growth of industrial mining footprint overtime has been attributed to external market demand influenced by market price, consumption and production at the global level (sonter et al, 2014a), economic climate of host country (O'Regan and Moles, 2006) and stability of the political landscape (Poteete,2009: Kumah, 2006). However, there have not been the adequate empirical studies to assess the impacts of relocating communities in other to help government to formulate policies that can be used to regulate/guide mining companies during the relocation process. In most cases, especially in the relocated communities of MABBEN, the impact of these relocation to their livelihood cannot be overemphasized comparatively to when they were in their original settlement. Some recounted the rich cultural, social, economic and environmental means of sustenance and living condition they were enjoying were taken away from them without any sustainable livelihood programme. Mining provides

direct and indirect employment opportunities for inhabitants within the mining communities thereby contributing to their livelihoods, however, the number of inhabitants employed vary depending on their skills and their connection to the authorities in the companies as well as the local authorities in their operating communities. This is where the locals feel the impact of their relocation to communities that does not offer them what they were enjoying in their original communities. Very few of the members of those communities gain full time employment while some obtain temporary, often short-lived jobs which often create some amount of insecurity considering the job, remuneration and the burden of security a better job. Meanwhile, it is safe to say that small-scale and large-scale mining companies contributes significantly to the local livelihoods of community members as it creates a lot of employment opportunities and directly/indirectly provides income for those who offer auxiliary services for the sector. Although mining can provide economic opportunities for local communities, its activities can have wide ranging undesirable environmental impacts with negative implications for local livelihood (Kotey & Rolfe, 2014; Sinha et al, 2007; Weldegiorgis & Ali, 2016). Negative livelihood impacts resulting from mining activities are more pervasive among the most vulnerable segments of the society (Akabzaa, 2000). Women and children often suffer the brunt of the negative impacts of these relocation as a result of these industrial mining activities in the MABBEN communities. They are usually unfairly treated when it comes to compensation and other programmes for the people of the relocated communities. Traditionally, family heads are men and most compensation for farm crops and houses usually goes to these family heads who mostly exercise a discretionary use of money. Women who are dependent on petty trading for their livelihood mostly lose such livelihood sources during relocation or resettlement and this is evident at the relocated communities of MABBEN as they find it difficult to make income substantial to support themselves and their families.

In response, alternative livelihood has emerged as a potential solution offering new opportunities for sustainable development. Various approaches have been adopted as the government of Sierra Leone (GoSL) has also updated the mines and minerals act of 2009 to the new Mines and Mineral development act 2023 to address some of these challenges faced by the communities affect by the corporate and industrial mining companies. Some of the provisions in the new act addresses the gaps that existed when some of the relocations were done and to also empower regulatory bodies to monitor the activities involved in the relocation in other to guarantee the livelihood of the relocated communities in a sustainable manner. Provisions in the new acts have now adopted approaches to ensure that the mining companies invest in the human resource and infrastructural development of the resident of those mining communities through a programme called CDAP (Community Development Action Plan). This is a programme that enhances the development needs of the community through a two-way approach that involves stakeholders of both parties (the community and the companies). Through engagement, they identify the most vulnerable projects that can augment the livelihood of the people and the company funds those projects through a certain percentage of funds that is annually allocated for such purposes. The alternative livelihood program may come in the form of economic empowerment of the residents so as to ensure their long-term economic sustenance (Guerra, 2002).

Thus, this research seeks to explore the impact of alternative livelihood programs in the relocated communities of MABBEN and to examine the potentials of alternative livelihoods to promote economic diversification, reduce vulnerability and enhance well-being. To be discussed in this paper are; the statement of the problem, rationale and need of the research, review of the related/previous literature, the conceptual and theoretical framework, the research methodology, analysis and findings, limitations, recommendation and finally bibliography and references.

Statement of the problem

Majority of the small and large-scale mining companies in Sierra Leone are faced with various problems related to concession, livelihood programmes and policies for the communities in which they operate considering the impact of their activities on the land. The daily environmental hazards caused by their mining activities results in both short- and long-term health risks couple with the fact that residents are left to wallow in abject poverty after the companies have claimed all what they want for their survival. These companies normally claim that the above are taken care of by the royalties paid to the government as well as 1% community development fund agreement which in turn does not get to the residents of the affected communities and sometimes those funds that are claimed to be paid by the companies are managed by the companies themselves leaving the affected communities in absolute doubt on how they arrived at the amount paid.

According to Temeng & Abew 2009, mining companies have begun to show some commitment to the well-being of residents in their catchment areas amidst the pressure from international organisations and national governments. In this regard, different programmes are being designed and implemented to enhance the livelihood of these communities, some of these programmes are in the form of donations, CDAP (Community Development Action Plan), infrastructural development, educational support and scholarships, farming and provision of utensils, provision of water and other interventions that will ensure the well-being of residents.

Despite these efforts by some of the companies, however, it is widely visible and evident that unemployment and the poverty levels in these relocated communities of MABBEN are among the highest in the country. It is also not clear how much has been achieved and the impact these programmes have created in uplifting the status of these communities.

This study seeks to explore the alternative livelihood programmes as a pathway of sustainable development of the relocated communities of MABBEN.

Rationale of the study

There are limited literatures on alternative livelihood for mining relocated communities in Sierra Leone, the rationale of this study is that it will add to the literatures, provide the basis for future research and generally add to the body of knowledge.

This study further gives insight on how residents/beneficiaries perceive the alternative livelihood programmes being implemented, proffer better ways and guides on how to provide sustainable alternative livelihood for resident of the relocated communities of MABBEN that will create the needed impact and lastly, the recommendations from the findings of this research can be used to improve on similar livelihood projects elsewhere in the country.

Literature review and gap analysis

This section covers a review of prior work on alternative livelihoods that aimed at reducing the poverty levels sustainably. It highlights the main concepts and topic under discussion in the study including sustainable livelihood in the relocated communities of MABBEN. The contents in this literature review includes relevant information on alternative livelihood in different fields of study, related impediments to sustainable alternative livelihood programmes, different livelihood approaches and the effects of mining activities on the livelihood of the relocated communities. The literatures consulted for this study were mainly sourced from selected academic journals, articles and books.

Sustainable livelihood

Sustainable livelihood is the way of living that allows individuals or communities access to their basic and current needs without compromising the ability of future generation to meet their own needs. Livelihood involves the capabilities, assets and activities necessary for a means of livelihood (Riel, 2015:8). A livelihood is sustainable when it can cope and recover from the shocks and maintain or enhances its capabilities and assets presently and in the future without undermining the natural resource base. There are three key elements that the definitions recognise, each relating to a wider literature with, in some cases, established way of assessing outcomes. The livelihood outcomes focus on linking concerns over work and employment with poverty reduction with broader issues of adequacy, security, well-being and capability (Solesbury, 2003).

Considering the numerous gaps that exists, a closer look at livelihood components utilising the sustainable livelihood framework (SLF) will prove to be very much useful as this approach is centered on securing decent livelihoods that contribute to the quality of peoples lives by recognising both a need for enhanced incomes and poor household's abilities to cope with risks and vulnerabilities. The current living condition of the people in the relocated communities pose serious concern to human habitation. They lack the basic needs as they live in dilapidated shelter and majority of them are not even assured of where their next meal will come from. A livelihood is key in people's lives and a critical tool in poverty alleviation. According to Carney (1998:4), it includes the capabilities, assets and activities necessary for a means of living. It is further indicated that sustainable livelihood approach encourages a deep understanding of various types of livelihood capital (physical, social, financial, natural and human) which require consideration when planning livelihood strategies within wider structures and institutions also known as policies, institutions and processes (Patnaik & Prasad, 2014). It is vital for studies attempting to eradicate poverty to consider the components such as livelihood assets, vulnerability aspect and institutions that intercedes assets and the vulnerability (Olajide 2015). Various studies on poverty have emphasized the need for the in-depth understanding of which assets are accessible and available to people. Unravelling the connections between the complex and dynamic processes and outcomes of different strategies is a key aspect of the investigation of sustainable livelihoods. One step in any such analysis requires an unpacking of each of the three core strategies to distinguish different dynamics and outcomes (Scoones, 1999). Socioeconomic difference of course exists within any site and these also have a major impact on the composition of livelihood portfolios (Solesbury,2003). A wide number of axes of difference are relevant including contrasts of asset ownership, income levels, gender, age, religious affiliation, caste, social or political status or so on. This may refer to differences in basic livelihood resources for access to different forms of capital.

Effects of mining on the livelihood of residents of the relocated communities of MABBEN

Mining has generally been noted to account for changes in both the physical landscape and the natural resources hence affecting the daily lives of the people living in mining areas (Aryee, 2001). In fact, the argument of whether mining is indeed the answer to economic problems on most communities have been deeply questioned. In most cases, the benefits of mining often largely accrue to the national economy and to the development of most urban areas and to the detriment of the host communities of which the relocated communities of MABBEN is not an exception. Problems that emanate from such situations are compounded by wrong signals eternal wealth which is sent to the population of other settlements who

troop to the mining centres in search of the non-existing wealth (Hilson & Yakovleva, 2007). This increases the population of the mining centres substantially without any improvement in the means of livelihoods but instead, deterioration.

Mining takes large share of the land area of the inhabitant of the mining communities and these lands are very fertile ones relied on by residents. Due to the large-scale of industrialized operation of these mining companies, communities were relocated and these relocations resulted in them being deprived of their means of livelihoods. A further deprivation of the residents is the pollution of water bodies, deforestation as well as infiltrating the communities with dust, noise, vibration and other chemicals that have long term implications for them. The aggregated effects of these are that the residents are indeed worse off with these large-scale mining activities than before by making them very vulnerable due to the activities that includes but not limited to the heavy blasting operations and the likes.

However, Hilson and Pardie (2006) tend to disagree with this assertion by indicating that mining can sometimes provide the impetus for the conservation of the environment through the provision of funding. Whatever the situation is, it is clear that mining substantially deprives the resident of the relocated communities of MABBEN of their livelihood and that the benefits cannot make for the mass losses hence such mining companies need to provide an integral means of alternative livelihood to the residents.

Alternative livelihoods and its approaches

The various effects of mining on the lives of residents in mining communities have led to unified voice calling for a more responsible approach on the part of the mining companies and the government to provide the residents with laws that can influence the dignified means of sustaining themselves. The biggest dividends can be achieved when human capital investments are in a secure environment while aligned with parallel investments in physical, financial, natural and social assets (Moser & Dani, 2008). In view of this, many mining companies around the world as well as government have begun designing alternative livelihood programmes for residents of mining communities.

Apparently, alternative livelihood is not only limited to the mining sector, other sectors like oil drilling, construction etc should all practice alternative livelihood programmes (Bush, 2009). This measure is often adopted as a stop gap measure by the industry giants in order to evade criticisms of neglecting the inhabitants and abandoning their corporate social responsibilities. It must however, be mentioned that it has been successfully planned and implemented in some cases where impacts on the well-being of the residents have been substantially positive (Arye,2001).

In implementing such programmes, different approaches have been adopted depending on the available resources, the residents' needs and capacity as well as the overall goal of the implementing agency. The main goal of alternative livelihood is to ensure the improvement of the standard of living of residents through providing them with other sources of income. Therefore, in achieving this, the right approach has to be adopted and the most acceptable approach that is widely accepted and followed is the approach that is economic in outlook. Alternative livelihood programmes have always been economic in outlook (Kitula, 2006). This approach ranges from alternative farming method such as new and improved farming methods with training in animal husbandry and the use of faming chemicals, training in traditional crafts and technical and vocational training (TECHVOC).

However, one key aspect needs to be taken into consideration when implementing alternative livelihood programmes, the sustainability aspect. To avoid failures in implementing sustainable livelihood programmes, one has to avoid the imposition of alternative programmes on the residents without a measure of what the residents' needs are (Tschakert, 2009).

Hilson and Porter (2005) summarized that the main objective of sustainable livelihood is to search for more effective methods to support people and communities in ways that are more meaningful to their daily lives and needs.

Conceptual and theoretical Framework

The framework of this study banks on the Sustainable livelihood framework advocated by Ian Scoones in 1998 which aids the analysis of sustainable livelihood and sustainable development. The concept assumes that the policies of the National Minerals Agency and the resettlement/relocation provisions in the Mines and minerals development act of 2023 should be undertaken. These policies and regulations when adhered to by mining companies will lead to the adoption of effective and efficient livelihood strategies (Alternative livelihood) combined with the livelihood resources (human, social, natural, physical and financial) to enhance a sustainable livelihood outcome. It is assumed that the nature of alternative Livelihood strategies to be adopted cannot be done without the involvement of the affected community because community participation will motivate the persons to fully appreciate and embrace the strategy implemented by the company or government. Scoones (1998) further propounded that implementation of livelihood strategies will fail woefully without the involvement of the affected community in all stages. Community participation is an additional variable of the alternative livelihood framework. Given the background of this study and the quest for a comprehensive livelihood in the relocated community of MABBEN, this framework was adopted as an analytical tool for understanding the way individuals and communities build, sustain and enhance their livelihoods and also creates the basis in identifying objectives and policies that are appropriate in terms of supporting livelihoods. The figure below depicts the key dimensions of sustainable livelihoods adopted by Scoones (1998). It shows how livelihood is sustainable when it can cope with and recover from shocks and stresses and enhance capabilities and assets both now and in the future thus making assets the building blocks of s sustainable livelihood. It thus draws attention to the variety of assets hat contributes to making a sustainable livelihood and the ways in which they are interdependent. It identifies five categories of assets; financial, social, physical, human and personal.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework as adopted by Ian Scoones (1998)

Where FA = Financial asset, SA = Social asset, HA= Human asset, PA = Practical asset and PHA= Physical asset

Figure 1 shows that there are two types of intervention (Strategic and Practical). Practical Interventions facilitates the efforts of low-income households to build their livelihood asset and they include education, employment, training, savings and support for businesses etc where as strategic interventions are changes towards the goal of social and economic change at the universal or systemic level.

The assets according to this framework encompasses financial assets which includes finance/savings, inflow of money from credit and access to credit etc. Social assets include networks, family support, friendships, relationships, partnerships and collaboration etc. Human assets include skills, knowledge, employability and earning power, good health and leadership. Physical assets look at secured shelter, affordable energy, information, basic consumer goods, affordable transportation etc while Personal assets comprise motivation, self-esteem, self-confidence, self-perception, emotional wellbeing and assertiveness. The diagram illustrates the enhancements in assets of the beneficiaries that before the introduction of livelihood programme, individuals are identified with few assets but improvements are made in the standard of living and the lives of the residents of the relocated communities.

Research Methodology

This research was done within the mixed method paradigm in which a case study design was used as an appropriate design method to enable the researcher to interact with key stakeholder within the communities as well as respondents from the affected communities. This aspect of the research will discuss the study area, research design, research questions, methods of data collection hypothesis, tools and testing.

Study area

The research was conducted in the Iron ore and gold mining communities known as the MABBEN communities located in Tonkolili District, northeast region of Sierra Leone, West Africa. The relocated communities of MABBEN are 1614 square kilometre situated between Koinadugu and Tonkolili district, MABBEN is an acronym for Mabontor (MA) the chiefdom headquarter of Simiria Chiefdom, Bumbuna (B) the chiefdom headquarter of Dansogoya Chiefdom and Bendugu (BEN) the chiefdom headquarter of Sambaia Chiefdom. Even though the MABBEN communities in a broader perspective comprises other chiefdoms like Kafe, Diang and Kalanthuba, the acronym was adopted for simplicity's sake to represent these six (6) mineral rich chiefdoms. These chiefdoms are rich in minerals and they serve as the host chiefdoms of the largest iron ore deposit in the sub-Saharan Africa and because of the industrial mining activities in these chiefdoms, communities were relocated from their original habitat to other communities as a result of the nature of the mining activities. With terrain that is undulating with hills rising above 500 meters above sea level, the hills are intersected with rivers and streams that the residents use for fishing and other economic activities but they have all been polluted by mining hence making residents vulnerable according to the concept of alternative livelihood. The increasing mining activities coupled with the destruction of farmlands which are the main sources of livelihood has rendered some of the residents vulnerable and poor.

To address this, the current alternative livelihood programmes that are being implemented needs to be improved and made to be sustainable thereby improving on the standard of living and wellbeing of the vulnerable and poor residents. The choice of the study area was therefore informed by the fact that steps must be taken to explore alternative livelihood as a pathway for sustainable development for the relocated communities of MABBEN.

Research Design

Given the background of this research and the quest for a comprehensive insight into livelihoods in the relocated communities of MABBEN, the sustainable livelihood framework (SLF) was adopted. This framework as cited in Olajide (2015) is used as an analytical tool to understand the way individuals and communities build, sustain and enhance their livelihoods and also create a basis in identifying objectives and policies that are appropriate in terms of supporting livelihoods.

A case study approach was undertaken using a cross-sectional design. In a cross-sectional design, either the entire population or a subset of the population is selected and from these individuals, data is collected to help answer research questions of interest. According to Mann (2003), cross sectional design helps to enrich a study because it helps to study a large number of people within a short period and determine the causes and prevalence of a phenomenon which other study design cannot do.

This design was used because data was collected from the respondents once within a specific period and it helped to assess the impact of alternative livelihood programmes implemented by mining companies on the lives of residents of the relocated communities without any manipulation of the study population.

Data Collection

Data collected provided information at both individual household level and community level. Essentially, the contribution from respondents to this study may directly or indirectly contribute to the creation of a collective poverty alleviation efforts.

A sample size of 50 respondents was used for this research. Considering the researchers limited time and resources, data collection activities were conducted in a systematic way. The targeted participants were preferably heads of households or people above the age of 18 years who were interviewed in stages. Forty-seven (47) respondents from within the affected communities were interviewed, two (2) respondents from one of the mining companies and one (1) government official working for the National Minerals Agency (NMA) were interviewed. Key information was obtained from respondents through interviews, observation, surveys and secondary sources as stated above. Interviews are very important in qualitative research especially in case studies as they help the researcher to capture direct quotations about people's perspectives and experiences. These valuable information hinge on possible interventions, planning, alternative livelihood programmes implemented and livelihood challenges.

Table 1: Distribution of sample size

Target population	Sample
National Minerals Agency (NMA)	1
Mining Companies	2
Affected communities	47
Total	50

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

Questions were structured in English and the interview guide was administered in a local language (Kuranko and Krio) to enable the respondents to express themselves well without language barrier and to feel at home with the interviewer. In order to cross check some of the information provided, observation was used only on the residents. The observation was done after the interview and some of the things that were observed were the living conditions of residents, their socio-economic status, the nature and state of their houses among other.

According to Mason (2002) this approach is most likely to assist in collecting in a naturally or situational or at least in a contextual to augment the data from the interviews.

Research Questions

Based on the objective of the research, the following research questions were formulated;

1. What economic activities were in place before the introduction of alternative Livelihood programmes?
2. What is the level of satisfaction with the previous economic activities?
3. What are the alternative livelihood programmes initiated?
4. Does this livelihood programmes create any impact in enhancing sustainable development?
5. What Challenges does these livelihood programmes come with?
6. What are your preferred alternative livelihood programmes that you think would enhance sustainable development in your communities?

Data Processing and Testing

Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) was applied to help with the analysis of data related to the objective of the research. Paton (2002) mentioned different forms of analysis which includes unique case orientation, holistic perspectives, context sensitivity, voice perspectives and reflexivity and inductive analysis and creativity synthesis. The process is done by defining variables and coding them as well as putting them into themes for easier analysis. The available qualitative data substantiated the statistics and findings from various sources.

Analysis and Discussion

This section of the research presents the analysis, results and discussion of the challenges, economic activities that were in place before the introduction of alternative livelihood programmes, nature and type of livelihood programmes, impact, challenges and the preferred livelihood that they think would enhance sustainable development in their communities.

Economic activities that were in place before relocation and introduction of alternative livelihood

Without a thorough understanding on previous economic activities that were in place before relocation, any alternative livelihood programme that is devised and implemented will encounter serious challenge because the success of alternative livelihood programmes has been found to correlate with the nature of the economic activities that were originally in place. The sustainability of alternative livelihood programmes has to be taken into consideration, that is why one has to analyse the correlation between the previous and the intended alternative livelihood programme. If the previous is found to be more appealing and preferable to the alternative livelihood, then the sustainability of any alternative livelihood is questionable. Therefore, it is essential to explore the previous economic activities in place and do some comparative analysis.

The respondents who were mainly residents of these relocated communities were asked to indicate their previous economic activity they were engaged in prior to the introduction of the alternative livelihood programme. Kitula (2006) postulated that it is important for any study that intends to measure the sustainability of alternative livelihood programmes not to only determine the previous economic activities but also to ascertain the extent to which the beneficiaries were satisfied with such activities as compared to alternatives offered by the livelihood programme.

Table 2 shows the various economic activities and the level of satisfaction

Table 2: Previous economic activities and level of satisfaction

Economic Activity	Respondents	Percentage %
Farming	24	48
Artisanal Mining	17	34
Petty Trading	6	12
Others	3	6
Total	50	100

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

The previous economic activities engaged in by the residents prior to their relocation and the introduction of alternative livelihood is as shown in Table 2 above. The evidences indicate that majority of the residents were initially engaged into farming (24) as an economic activity whilst artisanal mining activities constitutes the second highest. Petty trading is the third highest economic activities whilst others constitute the smallest number of residents engaged in other which comprises tailoring, hunting, carpentry etc.

This finding is consistent with the observation that most of the residents in the MABBEN communities have their original occupation they depend on for livelihood and such economic activities is mainly farming. Also, residents of MABBEN communities take artisanal mining as the second highest means of economic activities making the community very much attractive to outsiders who see mining as a source of employment and/or economic activities.

Table 3: Level of satisfaction with the previous economic activities

Economic Activity	Respondents	%	Level of satisfaction	
			Satisfied	Not satisfied
Farming	24	48	18	6
Artisanal Mining	17	34	15	2
Petty Trading	6	12	6	0
Others	3	6	2	1
Total	50	100	41	9

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

Kitula (2006) postulates that it is important for any study that intends to measure the sustainability of alternative livelihood not to only determine the previous economic activities but also to ascertain the extent to which satisfaction is derived from such activities as compared to the alternative livelihoods offered.

Table 3 indicates a high number of satisfactions for the farming activities they were engaged in as economic activities where as small number of respondents were not satisfied. This finding is consistent with the observation that residents are not satisfied with the unavailability of adequate land for their farming and other activities in the relocated communities as compared to the original settlement where they were not going through hurdles in the utilization of land for their economic activities. The table above shows that 41 out of the 50 respondents were satisfied with their previous economic activities.

Table 4: Alternative livelihood programme initiated. Did they implement these projects successfully?

Economic Activity	Respondents	%	Direct Answer		
			Yes	No	No idea
CDAP animal husbandry support	8	16	4	2	2

Women in Agriculture support	5	10	4	1	0
CDAP Scholarship	10	20	7	0	3
Water and Sanitation	14	28	13	0	1
Infrastructure	13	26	2	10	1
Total	50	100	30	13	7

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

Table 4 indicates the alternative livelihood initiated and whether the projects were implemented successful. From the table, majority of the respondents answered on the affirmative for the water and sanitation projects implemented as the most popular project that caters for all of the residents as it was only one respondent that seems not to have any idea on the successful implementation. The second highest programmed is the infrastructure which respondent expressed disagreement on as most of them responded in the negative that the projects are not implemented successfully, the CDAP scholarship also carried the third highest responded in the affirmative but the highest number of respondents said they don't have any idea on its implementation. The CDAP programme in animal husbandry carries the fourth response rate as 4 out of 8 said yes whilst two respondents said no and two respondents have no idea. Support to women in agriculture received the least response rate as 4 out of 5 responded in the affirmative whilst one responded in the negative.

Table 5: Impact of alternative livelihood programme in enhancing sustainable development

Economic Activity	Respondents	Agreement Rate		
		%	Agree	Disagree
Helpful but needs to cater for all and should be sustainable	12	24	8	4
It is not helpful because it captures only few people	18	36	16	2
Little or no benefit for the residents	15	30	12	3
It increases dependency rate	5	10	4	1
Total	50	100	40	10

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

The impacts of alternative livelihood on residents has long term implication for the sustainability of the alternative livelihood such that if the impacts are positive, there is the likelihood of the residents to continuously engage in it whilst they are likely to back out if the impacts are negative. The impacts of these alternative livelihood were measured and the result shows that majority of the respondents are of the view that the projects implemented are on focusing on few people and as such it is creating little impact on the residents of the relocated communities. In terms of the helpfulness of the alternative livelihood in enhancing sustainability, 8 out of 12 respondents agree that the alternative livelihood programmes have to be redesigned to cater for many residents and to ensure that it is designed to enhance sustainability. The dependency rate was also assessed and results show that it increases dependency rate thereby causing residents to depend on these programmed but ones they are implemented, it does not capture or provide benefit to majority of the residents.

Table 6: Challenges that comes with these alternative livelihood programme

Economic Activity	Respondents	%	Rate of Agreement%		
			Agree	Disagree	Neutral
Less attention and unsustainable	11	22	7	2	2
No regulation or policy to make it inclusive	9	18	7	1	1
Minimal/Less support to cater for all	17	34	17	0	0
Poor implementation by outsiders with less community collaboration	13	26	13	0	0
Total	50	100	44	3	3

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

Implementation of alternative livelihood programmes like other social interventions come with a lot of challenges from different aspect and background. These challenges may arise from stakeholders, resource constraints, regulatory agency and societal influences. The nature of the challenge will depend on the king of livelihood programmes introduced and the resources being exchanged.

Evidences from Table 6 shows that majority of the respondents agree to the challenges that comes with the alternative livelihood programmes whereas few disagreed and/or remain neutral. This therefore implies that respondents believed in their previous jobs as against the alternative means of livelihood. Even though they had their challenges in their previous engagements, they were confident that the challenges that comes with the alternative livelihood being implemented outweighs the previous sources of income in their original habitat.

Table 7: Preferred alternative livelihood programme that enhances sustainable development

Economic Activity	Respondents	Agreement %
Sustainable Agriculture including animal husbandry	13	26
Agro-Forestry	4	8
Entrepreneurship (Small and Medium Enterprises)	14	28
Renewable Energy	9	18
Technical and vocational Training	10	20
Total	50	100

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

As a pathway to sustainable development, table 7 shows the preferred alternative livelihood that can sustainably uplift the status of the relocated communities of MABBEN. Hilson and Porter (2005) states that the alternative livelihood programme has to be carved in the close association with the local economic environment and should emanate from within the community for it to be sustainable. It has therefore been argued that the success or failure of alternative livelihood programmes depends on the nature of the programmes themselves and how far they are able to improve on the well-being of the beneficiaries. In the table above,

28% of the respondents being the majority prefers small and medium entrepreneurship support as an alternative livelihood programme whilst 26% prefers sustainable agriculture which includes animal husbandry as technical and vocational training is the third highest alternative livelihood programme they preferred and renewable energy and Agro-forestry making the fourth and fifth respectively.

There is a sense of agreement with Hilson and Porter (2005) as the table above has proven that the beneficiaries of alternative livelihood programmes would carve a programme that depicts their previous livelihood in enhancing sustainable alternative livelihood programme.

Main Findings

- i. The main economic activities by the residents of the relocated communities were farming, artisanal mining, petty trading and others like hunting, carpentry, tailoring etc. Farming employed most of the residents followed by artisanal mining, petty trading and others.
- ii. Most of the respondents indicated that they were satisfied with their previous economic activities given the inadequate alternative livelihood programmes, inadequate availability of land for agricultural purposes and poor conditions of living in their current settlement.
- iii. Respondents highlighted the impact of the alternative livelihood being implemented, challenges and the preferred alternative livelihood programme to enhance sustainable development in the relocated communities of MABBEN
- iv. The research indicated that residents welcome the idea of alternative livelihood programme but it has to be inclusive and collaborative for the benefit of the affected residents.

Significance of the study

It is an incontestable fact that there are limited literatures on livelihood in Sierra Leone, this study will contribute to the recent debates on the roles of alternative livelihood in the economic well-being of the residents of the relocated mining communities as well as to make available the needed literature on the topics thereby laying the foundation for future research. Government institutions and civil society organizations usually advocate and implore on mining companies to create an environment wherein the affected communities are given opportunities but they mostly fail to provide the needed advise on what type of interventions and the methodology that these companies should embark on, discussions and findings in this study may serve as a guide to government institutions, non-governmental organizations and mining companies on how the perception of beneficiaries may influence the sustainability of alternative livelihood programmes. This could help companies and organizations to adopt measures so as to help deliver a positive impact on the lives of the affected communities. Finally, this study can be used as an important tool and serves as an eye-opener for company executives that are intending to implement alternative livelihood programme in their operational areas as it can be used for training purposes and the recommendations can be used to improve on similar projects in response to the prevailing poverty and inequality related challenges facing affected communities.

Limitations

Considering the deplorable road network in the MABBEN community couple with the fact that the expectation of resident has been marred by so many unfulfilled promises, conducting research in such environment comes with a lot of challenges. Therefore, a sound planning in terms of the scope of work was very much necessary to ensure that the researcher's limited resources produce the requisite data. Other notable limitations that this research encountered were;

- i. Hesitation in providing the required information by some stakeholders. Some respondents had to wait for concrete assurance that there would not be any negative repercussion.

- ii. Some of the respondents seek financial inducement before providing relevant information
- iii. Because of the limited literature in alternative livelihood, some of the views from the various literature review may not be entirely representative of the actual status of the MABBEN communities, this may however create some slight disparities in the context in which they were used in the review.
- iv. The research was somehow time consuming as a result of the road condition
- v. Weather condition was also not favourable as the research was conducted during the raining season. In most times, the researcher had to improvise during moments of stormy weather condition.

Recommendations

In consonance with the findings of this study couple with the fact that livelihoods are very much essential in people's lives and a key element in alleviating poverty, the following recommendation is therefore put forward;

- i. Government and other development partners should work towards development a policies and/or laws that can compel mining companies to embark on sustainable alternative livelihood that can uplift the status of the affected communities thereby alleviating poverty.
- ii. It is highly recommended that the implementation of alternative livelihood programmes should focus on addressing issues to best address the needs of the affected communities. Alternative livelihood programmes should not be implemented for media coverage or PR advantages but for the sustainable development of the affected communities thereby yielding the needed impact.
- iii. A stronger collaboration should be made with resident of the affected communities and their local expertise should be harnessed in the implementation of alternative livelihood programmes.
- iv. Implementation of alternative livelihood creates employment and alleviate poverty. This reduces the urge from residents to seek low-income jobs elsewhere.
- v. This study adds to the limited literatures on alternative livelihood and adds to the ongoing academic discourse, however, future studies can explore the future intentions of residents to continue with alternative livelihood programmes thereby serving as a significant measure for the future sustainability of alternative livelihood programmes in the country.
- vi. Capacitating traditional and local authorities with the required knowledge and skills that would increase community participation in implementing alternative livelihood adds value and enhance sustainable development.

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